

Reaction of Alexeenko and Krasnodarsky to exogenous gibberellic acid.

	Krasnodarsky 424	Krasnodarsky 424 + GA (0.001%)	Alexeenko	Alexeenko + GA (0.001%)
RNA, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	5.693	5.399	6.485	4.470
DNA, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	1.047	1.072	0.968	0.860
RNA/DNA, leaves	5.4	5.0	6.7	5.2
RNA, seedling roots (mg/g fresh matter)	6.417	9.313	4.612	7.375
DNA, seedling roots (mg/g fresh matter)	0.969	1.674	0.647	1.028
RNA/DNA, roots	6.6	5.6	7.1	7.2
Protein, seedling leaves (% of fresh matter)	6.4	5.2	7.1	4.3
Protein, seedling roots (% of fresh matter)	6.2	5.6	4.4	7.4
Chlorophyll, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	1.8	0.9	1.6	1.0
Carotenoids, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.3
Silica, mature plant straw (% of dry matter)	6.0		20.0	

length of the first real leaf sheath was measured.

Alexeenko had six times more reaction to exogenous GA than Krasnodarsky 424 (Fig. 2), perhaps because of the possible transformation of endogenous gibberellins biosynthesis genes which may have decreased gene activity. This transformation also changed plant morphology, nucleic acid and protein metabolism, pigment content, and silica content of straw from mature plants (see table).

Alexeenko will be used in breeding semidwarf rice varieties. □

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Field screening for sheath blight and rice root nematode resistance

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Ten rice varieties were field screened for resistance to sheath blight (ShB) (*Rhizoctonia solani*) and rice root nematode (*Hirschmanniella oryzae* Soltwedel, Luc and Goodey) at the State Seed Farm, Adoor, Kerala, where both problems are common. It was observed that high nematode incidence encourages severe ShB infection.

Table 1. Reaction of rice varieties to sheath blight.

Variety	Hill infection (%)	Disease index
Bharati	57	1.34
Rohini	60	1.77
Sabari	58	2.04
CO 25	69	2.77
IR8	70	3.27
Annapurna	73	3.29
Jaya	74	3.37
Triveni	72	4.56
PTB12	77	5.06
Jyothi	78	6.73
CD	1.371	0.536

Table 2. Population of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in roots of different rice varieties.

Variety	Nematodes/10-g root sample	
	Healthy plants	Diseased plants
PTB12	3.45	4.19
Annapurna	2.83	4.28
Triveni	4.04	4.32
Jaya	3.50	5.03
Bharati	3.81	5.37
Sabari	3.44	5.55
Rohini	4.98	5.65
CO 25	4.56	5.81
IR8	4.18	6.08
Jyothi	3.46	6.22
CD	0.445	0.853

Disease intensity and percent hill infection were recorded for both problems, using standard methods.

Bharati and Rohini had significantly lower levels of disease intensity, followed by Sabari, CO 25, IR8, Annapurna, and Jaya (Table 1). Maximum disease intensity was recorded for Triveni, PTB12, and Jyothi. Bharati, Sabari, and Rohini also had significantly lower hill infection. All varieties were susceptible to rice root nematode (Table 2). Roots of plants with ShB had

significantly more nematodes than roots of healthy plants (Table 2).

Trials conducted at IRRI indicate only a few rice varieties have ShB resistance. In Kerala, not one of 36 evaluated have ShB resistance. □

Leaf scald disease of rice at Ponnampet, Karnataka, India

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Ponnampet is a high-elevation area near the Malnad Mountains of India. Rice cultivation is intensive and blast disease is a serious problem. During 1982 kharif, leaf scald (LSc) (caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*) incidence was higher than normal in experimental plots and farmers' fields.

We tested 20 rice cultivars for resistance to LSc at the Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, during 1982 kharif. Plot size was 1.2 × 4.5 m and cultivars were planted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Intan and BKB were resistant checks and Cauvery and Tellahamsa were

Reaction of promising rice cultures to leaf scald disease.

Cultivar	Cross	Disease reaction ^a	Cultivar	cross	Disease reaction ^a
		<i>Resistant</i>			
5742	Imp. Sabarmathi/ Sona	3	574 1	Imp. Sabarmathi/ Sona	4
6903	RP5-32/Pankaj	3	6466	Dasal/IR20	4
7150	(PTB10/N136-19) Pankaj	3	7191	RP5-32/Pankaj	5
VL8	–	2	BKB	BKB	4
Rasi	TN1/Co 29	3	KMP106	75-203/IR34	6
Jaya	TN1/T141	2	IR54	–	6
Intan	–	3			<i>Susceptible</i>
KMS5914	Sona/Mahsuri	2	6 254	IR20/IR5-1143	7
		<i>Moderately susceptible</i>	6919	Pankaj/RP270-63-3	8
6056	CR44-35/W12708	5	7296	–	7
			Cauvery	–	8
			Tellahamsa	–	7

^aCD at 5% = 1.89, SEM = 0.94, CV% = 7.23, GM = 18.40. ^a By 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

susceptible checks. Plants were exposed to natural infection and disease incidence was rated using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. The results are in the table. □

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Brown planthopper-resistant japonica varieties developed in Korea

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In Korea, where brown planthopper (BPH) is the most serious rice insect, only hybrid cultivars have been released to farmers as resistant varieties. Among the released cultivars are several japonica varieties, but they are all susceptible to BPH.

Japonica varieties Milyang 64, Milyang 65, and Milyang 66 were developed as new elite lines at Yeongnam Crops Experiment Station in 1981. Milyang 64 was produced from a cross between Milyang 15 and Chok 48-1, and Milyang 65 and 66 were developed from crosses between Milyang 15 and Chok 48-5.

Seedling reactions of rice varieties to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3 were studied using the seedling bulk test. BPH biotype population increase was tested in a screen-house.

Milyang 64 and 66 were resistant to biotypes 1 and 2 at seedling stage and Milyang 65 was resistant to biotype 1 (Tables 1 and 2). □

Table 1. Reaction of japonica varieties to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3.

Variety	Damage rating ^a		
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Milyang 64 (Milyang 15/Chok 48-1)	R	R	S
Milyang 65 (Milyang 15/Chok 48-5)	R	S	S
Milyang 66 (Milyang 15/Chok 48-5)	R	R	S
Milyang 23 (check)	S	S	S
Cheongcheongbyeo (check)	R	S	R
Milyang 63 (check)	R	R	S

^aBased on seedling bulk test. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Population buildup of BPH biotypes on rice plants infested at 30 days after transplanting in the nethouse.

Variety	Populations ^a (no.)					
	Biotype 1			Biotype 2		
	45 DT	60 DT	75 DT	45 DT	60 DT	75 DT
Milyang 64	0.2	2.3	2.0	7.3	270.3	–
Milyang 65	3.0	3.8	3.5	55.0	950.0	HB
Milyang 66	1.3	0.6	3.5	1.4	160.0	–
Milyang 23 (check)	46.0	330.0	HB	125.0	HB	HB
Cheongcheongbyeo (check)	0.1	2.0	3.2	25.1	1200.0	HB
Milyang 63 (check)	0.1	1.4	0.2	0.1	110.01	–

^aTotal number of insects per hill. DT = days after transplanting. HB = hopperburned.

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